

A STUDY ON THE EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY IN COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

Motivation is the force that makes us do things this is a result of our individual needs being satisfied so that we have inspiration to complete the task. These needs vary from person to person as everybody has their individual needs to motivate themselves. Motivation can have an effect on the output of the business and concerns both quantity and quality. The business relies heavily on the efficiency of the production employees to make sure that products are manufactured in numbers that meet demand for the week. If these employees lack the motivation to produce completed products to meet the demand, then a problem leading to disastrous consequences are faced. This study is about the employee motivation with special reference to manufacturing industry in Coimbatore. Primary data collection was done through structural questionnaire. Secondary data was collected from company records, and websites. Research design used in this study was descriptive. Random sampling method was followed. Statistical tools applied are Simple percentage analysis, Chi-square were done using SPSS. The conclusion is that the employees are satisfied with the possibilities for increase in the salary or incentives part. These will reflect in the working conditions of the employees and the production will also be effected.

Key Words: Business, Employees & Salary

Introduction:

Motivation is a basic psychological process. Many experts in the field of Organizational behavior often relate a person's behavior with motivation. They believe that a person's behavior considerably influenced by the extent of his motivation through motivation is not only the explanation of behavior. Just like all other cognitive processes motivation cannot be seen only behavior can be seen. Employee motivation can be understood as the willingness to exert high levels of efforts towards organizational goals, conditioned by the efforts ability to satisfy some individual need. In a different context we can say that by motivating a person, we try to induce him into action, by stimulating his interest and through process.

Statement of Problem:

Motivation is an essential tool to vitalize the workers. The company has adapted payment, non-monetary method like good working conditions, amenities recognition transport facility etc. are provided. It is necessary to find whether these measures are having any impact on the workers efficiency and productivity.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know about the company motivation factors and the level of employees motivation in manufacturing industry in Coimbatore.
- ✓ To analyze overall expectations of the employee from the employer as a motivating element.
- ✓ To suggest the organization to increase the level of motivation among the employee.

Scope of the Study:

This is to emphasize that there is much scope for further studies in this area with or without modification in the sample size, data collection method etc. By using these methodologies further steps can be taken for more developments by studying the employee's motivation. There is scope for other companies to study their employee's motivation level by adopting the same methodology. The study will bring the light in presence or absence of motivation in the selected organization. It will measure the attitude of workers about motivation adopted by the company. The finding will be useful for the management for making decisions to improve the motivation.

Research Methodology:

Sample Design: Simple Random Sampling is selected for the study.

Data Collection:

- ✓ Primary Data: The Primary data collected for research study was collected through structured questionnaire survey technique were used to collect data. The questionnaire was structured and direct as to make the respondents understand it easily.
- ✓ Secondary Data: The secondary data collection for research study was collected from books and net surfing. The secondary data's consist of information that was been collect by company records some

text. Researchers usually start the investigation by examining secondary data, which provides a starting point for researchers.

Sample Size: A sample of 80 respondents has been taken for the study.

Sample Method: Random sampling method has been adopted under the non-probability sampling techniques and about 80 samples have been selected for this study.

Statistical Tools Used: Simple Percentage Analysis and Chi – Square test

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Since the attitude of the employees is bound to change so the result of this study may not be durable.
- ✓ The findings and observations made in this study are purely based on the respondent’s answers.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
Gender	Male	51	64
	Female	29	36
	Total	80	100
Age	Above 25- 35	12	15
	Above 36-45	26	32
	Above 46-55	23	29
	56 and above	19	24
	Total	80	100
Salary of the respondents	<5000	8	10
	5001-15000	16	20
	15001-25000	20	25
	25001-35000	16	20
	Above 35000	20	25
	Total	80	100
Opinion of the employees about the support provided by the management.	Yes	52	65
	No	28	35
	Total	80	100
Satisfaction about the salary	Strongly Agree	10	12
	Agree	32	40
	Neutral	12	15
	Disagree	15	19
	Strongly Disagree	11	14
	Total	80	100

Interpretation:

63 % of the employees are Male and 36 % of the employees are Female. 15 % of them are above 25-35, 32% of them are above 36-45, 29 % of them are above 46-55 and 24 % of them are 56 and above. 10% of the employees are getting less than 5000, 20% of the employees are receiving between 5001-15000, 25% of them are getting 15001-25000, 20% of them are getting between 25001-35000 and 25% of them are getting between above 35000. 65% of the employees accept that they are satisfied and 35% of the employees state that they are not satisfied.

Chi-Square Test with Age and Opinion about the Training Provided by the Superiors:

Age	Training Provided by superiors					Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Above 25-35	6	4	2	0	0	12
Above 36-45	12	8	0	5	1	26
Above 46-55	12	5	3	2	1	23
56 and Above	7	1	6	3	2	19
Total	37	18	11	10	4	80

Null Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no association between Age and Training provides by superiors.

Alternate Hypothesis:

H₁: There is a association between Age and Training provides by superiors.

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$

Chi-Square Test:

	Value	DF	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	17.278	12	.139

Inference:

The asymptotic significance is greater than .05. So we accept the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no association between Age and Training provides by superiors.

Chi-Square Test with Age and Opinion of the Employees about Motivation:

Age	Importance of Motivation					Total
	Most Important	Very Important	Neutral	Less Important	Not Important	
Above 25-35	4	2	4	1	1	12
Above 36-45	6	9	3	4	4	26
Above 46-55	7	2	5	5	4	23
56 and Above	4	6	3	4	2	19
Total	21	19	15	14	11	80

Null Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no association between Age and Importance of Motivation

Alternate Hypothesis:

H₁: There is an association between Age and Importance of Motivation

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$

Chi-Square Test:

	Value	DF	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.878	12	.713

Inference:

The asymptotic significance is greater than .05. So we accept the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no association between Age and Importance of Motivation.

Chi-Square Test with Gender and Motivation helps to win Co-Operation and Team Work:

Gender	Motivation Helps					Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Male	19	7	12	5	8	51
Female	16	4	2	5	2	29
Total	35	11	14	10	10	80

Null Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no association between Gender and Motivation helps.

Alternate Hypothesis:

H₁: There is an association between Gender and Motivation helps.

Level of Significance: $\alpha = 0.05$

Chi-Square Test:

	Value	DF	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.240	4	.182

Inference:

The asymptotic significance is greater than .05. So we accept the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no association between Gender and Motivation helps.

Findings:

- ✓ From the total sample employees 63.75 % of them are Male.
- ✓ About 32 % of the respondents are in between age of 36-45.
- ✓ 25% of the employees are getting a salary between 15001-25000 and above 35000.
- ✓ 35 % of respondent are not satisfied with the support from the management.
- ✓ 48 % of the employees are not satisfied with the salary which is provided in the organization.
- ✓ 43 % of the respondent are not satisfied with the working condition provide in the organization
- ✓ 48 % of the respondent are not satisfied with the retirement benefit provide in the organization.
- ✓ 37 % of the respondents are not satisfied with the medical benefit given by the organization.
- ✓ 49 % of the respondents are not satisfied with leaves provided by the organization.
- ✓ 39 % of the respondents are not satisfied with task and responsibility given to the employees in the organization.
- ✓ 44 % of the respondents are not satisfied with the incentive given by the organization.
- ✓ 47 % of the respondents are not satisfied with the rewards and recognized.
- ✓ 32 % of the respondents are not satisfied with the training provided by the superiors help to contribute more.
- ✓ 31 % of the respondents are not satisfied with the career advancement.
- ✓ 50 % of the respondents says that motivation helps to improve employee's ability.

- ✓ 22 % of the respondents says that salary fixation is not done through the capability of employee.
- ✓ 42 % of the respondents are not satisfied with motivation helps to win co-operation, teamwork.
- ✓ 39 % of the responsible are not satisfied with the training which increase the level of motivation of the employees.

Findings of Chi-Square Analysis:

- ✓ There is no association between Age and Opinion about the training provides by superiors.
- ✓ There is no association between Age and Opinion of the employees about motivation.
- ✓ There is no association between Gender and opinion about the motivation helps to win co-operation and team work.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The companies can provide better retirement benefit to an employee, to increase the motivation level.
- ✓ The company can give the better training program like, on the job training to the employees to increase the motivation level.
- ✓ The company can provide better medical benefit like monthly medical check up to the employees to increase the motivation level.
- ✓ The company can provide a good leave plan to increase the level of motivation.
- ✓ Try to respect the views of the employees to increase the level of motivation.

Conclusion:

The employees are satisfied with the retirement plans and about the possibilities for increase in the salary or incentives part. These will reflect in the working conditions of the employees and the production will also be effected. The Companies has to develop or adopt certain changes in the salary of the employees. Because everyone works for the monetary benefit for the welfare of their own family. Therefore, the salary should be concentrated by the company. And the next concept that the Organizations should focus on the leave plans adopted in the Companies. By doing certain changes in the leave plans of the organization will develop better relation between the employees and the Organizations.

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